

Supplemental information for

The map behind the roadmap: Introducing a geospatial energy model for utility-scale solar and wind power buildout

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1. Supplemental experimental procedures

1.1. Annual demand profiles and demand projections

This study uses a single demand profile, applied to all years of the time horizon considered. The reference demand profile was provided by the LCPDP team and is the demand profile of the Kenyan grid for the year 2021 at hourly time resolution. The total annual base demand is based on historical data for the years 2019, 2020, and 2021. The low and high demand scenarios used in this study are based on two demand scenarios of the LCPDP from 2022-2041 ¹, to which the reader is referred for more details. From 2042 to 2050, the average annual growth rate projected for the period 2031-2041 in the respective scenario is considered.

In terms of storyline, the low and high demand scenarios represent the following:

- Low demand: reference scenario based on historical data trends and expected economic development.
- High demand: ambitious growth scenario based on an accelerated development, aligned with the Vision 2030 growth projections and the successful implementation of the related flagship projects. The Vision 2030 growth projections foresee 99% of Kenyans obtaining access to electricity by 2030.

1.2. Cost assumptions for solar and wind utility-scale power plants

Solar and wind investment costs for the year 2019 are obtained either from site-specific data provided by the LCPDP team (see Kihara et al. ² for details) or from Sterl et al ³. In the case of additional grid and road buildout investment costs for generic capacity modelled through the Model Supply Region methodology. In the case of solar panels, the same capital cost is considered for all power plants, and the cost variations among different sites are only due to the grid-connection costs from Sterl et al ³. On the other hand, the cost of wind turbines depends on their class, and hence on the average wind speed at the site³.

To project cost reductions in VRE CAPEX towards 2050, the Net Zero and Stated Policy scenarios from the World Energy Outlook are considered ⁴. For both scenarios, as the WEO does not have Africa-specific cost data, the global average in 2030 and 2050 is considered.

The annual discount rate considered is 8.9%, as used in Kihara et al. ².

1.3. Assumption for reserve margins contributions in FlexTool

The reserve margin contributions of the different power plants are presented in Table S1. Unless a number is specified, FlexTool reserve margin contributions are the same as the ones in OsEMOSYS. The reason for the different assumptions is linked to the time resolution: FlexTool models the power system at an hourly level, while OsEMOSYS aggregates hours in representative time slices. Thus, the amount of reserve needed for each hour and the availability to provide this reserve from each power plant is much more detailed in FlexTool. For instance, the reserve margin contributions from solar and wind are based on, and applied to, their hourly curtailment in FlexTool, while OsEMOSYS cannot provide this level of resolution.

1.4. Timeslices structure in OSeMOSYS

The general structure of the timeslices used in the OSeMOSYS model is based on the one in the work by Kihara et al.², with the addition of the weak wind season, as outlined in the “OSeMOSYS description” subsection of the “Experimental procedures” section in the main text. A detailed description of the seasons, day types and day splits contributing to define the timeslices is given in Table S3. A complete list of the timeslices and their relative weight with respect to the entire year is given in Table S7.

1.5. Assumption for capacity of transmission lines in FlexTool

In investment mode, the maximum capacities of the different transmission lines increase over time as shown in Table S6. For 2030, each line can be expanded up to 50% above its base year capacity. For the 2050 low-demand case, investments are allowed up to 3 times the base year capacity except for the transmission between Mt Kenya and Coast. Due to its significantly lower base year capacity (225 MW) compared to the others (e.g., 4 GW between Nairobi and West), the constraint is relaxed to 20 times the base year capacity. This adjustment ensures a total maximum capacity of a similar magnitude as other lines (around 4.5 GW, which is slightly less than half of the total 2019 capacity for all transmission lines). For the 2050 high-demand case, the multiplication factor is increased to 6 to reflect the roughly double demand compared to the low-demand case.

2. Supplemental tables and figures

Table S1: Contribution to the reserve margin from each power plant technology included in the models, expressed as a percentage of the total capacity installed of that plant except where otherwise indicated. In the FlexTool column, we only indicate the instances where the number used is different from OSeMOSYS.

Technology	Reserve margin contribution	
	OSeMOSYS	FlexTool
Batteries	75%	100%
Biomass	100%	
Coal	100%	
Geothermal	100%	
Heavy and light fuel oil	100%	
Hydro – Dam	100%	
Hydro – Run of river	0%	100%
Natural gas	100%	
Nuclear	100%	
Pumped hydro	75%	
Solar	0%	50% of instantaneous curtailment
Wind	0%	50% of instantaneous curtailment

Table S2: Inertia constants and minimum loads in FlexTool

Technology	Inertia constant (MWs/MW)	Minimum load (%)
Biomass	3	50
Coal	3.3	40
Geothermal	1.06-1.14	75
Fuel Oil	2-6.2	5-30
Hydropower	1.5-3.2	0-25
Natural Gas	6.3	6-15
Nuclear	5	50

Table S3: Definition of seasons, day types and day splits concurring to the definition of timeslices in the OSeMOSYS model. The relative weight for each category adds up to unity, corresponding to a full year, week, or day. For seasons, the number of days corresponds to the number of days within the time period considered minus the number of weak wind days that fell within that season.

Definitions	Number of days or hours	Relative weight
Seasons		
Dry (Jan – Mar)	75	0.205
Wet 1 (Apr – May)	45	0.124
Int (Jun – Sep)	121	0.331
Wet 2 (Oct – Dec)	88	0.241
Weak wind (10% weakest wind days)	36	0.100
Day type		
Weekdays	5	0.7143
Weekend days	2	0.2857

Day splits		
A (00:00 – 06:00)	6	0.250
B (06:00 – 09:00)	3	0.125
C (09:00 – 15:00)	6	0.250
D (15:00 – 19:00)	4	0.167
E (19:00 – 21:00)	2	0.083
F (21:00 – 00:00)	3	0.125

Table S4: Average wind CF per cluster and per season in OSeMOSYS, including the virtual weak wind season implemented to capture wind droughts. Note that the numbers given per season are given before corrections for losses and calibration to LDCPD data. A complete list of capacity factor per cluster per timeslice both for wind and solar is given in Table S8.

Wind cluster	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10
Average wind power CF from raw cluster data										
Season 1 (Jan-Mar)	48.7%	80.8%	64.2%	77.3%	49.3%	70.3%	37.6%	59.8%	65.8%	57.2%
Season 2 (Apr-May)	44.7%	44.8%	64.2%	69.8%	54.6%	54.5%	56.5%	36.2%	36.4%	54.0%
Season 3 (Jun-Sep)	79.1%	57.5%	91.0%	83.2%	71.9%	75.4%	89.8%	56.2%	60.3%	75.4%
Season 4 (Oct-Dec)	62.7%	84.2%	79.5%	90.9%	56.2%	86.2%	47.9%	76.6%	79.0%	72.5%
Season 5 (weak wind)	4.3%	29.1%	7.6%	23.3%	22.6%	20.5%	9.6%	24.0%	11.1%	11.4%
Yearly average	59.5%	66.3%	74.0%	78.9%	57.9%	71.2%	58.7%	57.7%	60.4%	64.3%
After applying corrections (this paper)										
Yearly average ¹	49.3%	55.0%	61.4%	65.5%	48.1%	59.1%	48.7%	47.9%	50.1%	53.3%
Yearly average ²	41.8%	46.6%	52.0%	55.4%	40.7%	50.0%	41.2%	40.5%	42.4%	45.1%

¹ After loss corrections

² After calibration to LCPDP data (cf. Table 2 in main text)

Table S5: Penalty assumptions in FlexTool

Loss of load [\$/MWh]	Loss of reserves [\$/MWh]	Lack of inertia [\$/MWs]	Lack of capacity [\$/MW]	Curtailement [\$/MWh]
1,500	1,000	15,000	1,000	250

Table S6: Maximum capacities for the Kenyan transmission lines in MW

Line	Base Year	2030	2050	
			Low demand	High demand
West - Nairobi	4,000	6,000	16,000	28,000
Mt Kenya - Nairobi	911	1,367	3,644	6,377
Mt Kenya - Coast	225	338	4,725	4,725
Coast - Nairobi	3,063	4,595	12,252	21,441

Figure S1: Annual installed capacity and annual activity for each technology type, as obtained from OSeMOSYS. Same graphs as included in Figure 1 in the main text but extended to include all four scenarios modelled. Columns 1 and 2 correspond to Figure 1 and to the scenarios S1 and S2 analysed in the main text. Columns 3 and 4 report the results for scenarios S3 and S4, built with the same low and high demand projections but with higher projected costs for solar and wind power plants.

Figure S2: Annual solar (first row) and wind (second row) installed per each MSR cluster, as obtained from OSeMOSYS. Same graphs as included in Figure 2 in the main text but extended to include all four scenarios modelled. Columns 1 and 2 correspond to Figure 2 and to the scenarios S1 and S2 analysed in the main text. Columns 3 and 4 report the results for scenarios S3 and S4, built with the same low and high demand projections but with higher projected costs for solar and wind power plants.

References

1. Ministry of Energy (2022). *Updated Least Cost Power Development Plan, Study Period: 2022-2041*.
2. Kihara, M. *et al.* Mid- to long-term capacity planning for a reliable power system in Kenya. *Energy Strategy Reviews* **52**, 101312 (2024).
3. Sterl, S. *et al.* An all-Africa dataset of energy model “supply regions” for solar photovoltaic and wind power. *Sci Data* **9**, 664 (2022).
4. IEA. *World Energy Outlook 2022 – Analysis*. <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2022> (2023).